

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF VIBRATION AND DAMPING
FOR SYMMETRIC COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The vibration and damping characteristics of composite laminates have been investigated by the finite element method based on the shear deformable theory. The complex eigenvalue problem based on the linear viscoelasticity has been solved using a modal approach which can save tremendous amount of computation time. The developed computer program which can predict the natural frequencies, the modal loss factors and the complex modal vectors, gives accurate results. The effect of the fiber orientation on the natural frequencies and the modal loss factors is investigated.

KEYWORDS: Complex Modulus; Damping; Finite Element Analysis; Modal Approach; Viscoelastic.

1. INTRODUCTION

In general, materials with high stiffness are of low damping while materials with high damping are of low stiffness. However, the advanced composite materials have not only high stiffness but also high damping property, since high stiffness can be obtained from fiber and high damping from matrix such as polymer. The dominant mechanism of damping in composite materials includes the internal friction within the constituents and interfacial slip at the fiber-matrix interfaces. Specially, the damping in composite materials plays an important role in controlling the resonant response of aerospace structures and thus in prolonging their service life under repeated loading or impact condition [1].

Research on the damping analysis of composites is not so sufficient as that on the free vibration analysis. Gibson and Plunkett [2] reviewed experimental and analytical efforts to characterize the dynamic properties of fiber-reinforced composite materials. Damped element model [3] was used to predict the damping of composite laminates. Recently, Bicos and Springer [4] introduced the damped element model into a shell structure. Hashin [5] applied the elastic-viscoelastic correspondence principle to relate the elastic moduli and creep compliances of the viscoelastic composites. The complex modulus, which consists of a real part representing elastic stiffness and an imaginary part representing dissipation, is widely used to model the

behavior of linear viscoelastic materials under sinusoidal vibration. Alam and Asnani [6, 7] utilized the concept of the complex modulus for the vibration and damping analysis for composite plates and shells by series solution. Malhotra *et. al.* [8] studied also damping characteristics of orthotropic triangular plates by using the complex moduli and three-noded triangular finite elements.

In this paper, the shear deformable plate theory is applied to the vibration and damping analysis of fiber-reinforced composite laminates. The complex eigenvalue problem based upon the linear viscoelasticity is formulated by finite element method. The modal approach to damping analysis of composite laminates is introduced to save computation time by reducing the large degrees of freedom of the complex eigenvalue problem using finite element method. The developed computer program can predict the natural frequencies, the modal loss factors and the complex modal vectors. The results obtained under the assumption that the material properties in the fiber direction are perfectly elastic and the others are viscoelastic, are also examined to see if the reasonable modal loss factors are obtained.

2. THEORY

2.1 Complex modulus of lamina Damping is a quality inherent in all known materials and is the mechanism of energy dissipation. It affects the dynamic response severely near the resonant frequency. The damping of a given structures has at least four different sources [9]. First, and our concern, is "material damping", which is present in any material and is the minimum level that total damping can achieve. Next comes "structural damping", which occurs when two or more neighboring components of structure rub against each other while vibrating. A third mechanism is "viscous damping", where dissipation occurs by motion within a fluid. Finally, "Coulomb damping" occurs when some part of a structure slides along a boundary or interface. Definitions of damping are various according to testing method and their relationship is as follows:

$$\eta = \frac{\Psi}{2\pi} = \frac{E^I}{E^R} = \tan \gamma = 2\zeta = \frac{\omega_2^2 - \omega_1^2}{2\omega_n^2} \quad (1)$$

where η and Ψ are loss factor and specific damping capacity, respectively. E^R is a real part and E^I is an imaginary part of complex modulus as shown in Fig. 1.

Stieltjes integral equation in the viscoelasticity yields [10]

$$\sigma_{ij}(t) = C_{ijkl}(0) \epsilon_{kl}(t) + \int_0^t \epsilon_{kl}(t-\tau) \frac{dC_{ijkl}(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (2)$$

Taking Fourier transform of Eq. (2),

$$\sigma_{ij}^*(\omega) = C_{ijkl}(0)[1 + i\omega C_{ijkl}^*(\omega) / C_{ijkl}(0)] \epsilon_{kl}^*(\omega) \quad (3)$$

where * denotes Fourier-transformed complex variables.

Therefore, the complex moduli of an orthotropic material for structural damping are defined as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} E_1^* &= E_1 (1 + i \eta_1), & E_2^* &= E_2 (1 + i \eta_2), \\ G_{12}^* &= G_{12} (1 + i \eta_{12}), & G_{13}^* &= G_{13} (1 + i \eta_{13}), & G_{23}^* &= G_{23} (1 + i \eta_{23}) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The constitutive relations in x-y coordinates shown in Fig. 2 become

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x^* \\ \sigma_y^* \\ \tau_{xy}^* \end{Bmatrix}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11}^* & \bar{Q}_{12}^* & \bar{Q}_{16}^* \\ \bar{Q}_{16}^* & \bar{Q}_{22}^* & \bar{Q}_{26}^* \\ \bar{Q}_{16}^* & \bar{Q}_{26}^* & \bar{Q}_{66}^* \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x^* \\ \epsilon_y^* \\ \gamma_{xy}^* \end{Bmatrix}_k, \quad \begin{Bmatrix} \tau_{yz}^* \\ \tau_{zx}^* \end{Bmatrix}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{44}^* & \bar{Q}_{45}^* \\ \bar{Q}_{45}^* & \bar{Q}_{55}^* \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{yz}^* \\ \gamma_{zx}^* \end{Bmatrix}_k. \quad (5)$$

2.2 Finite element formulation Using the YNS plate theory [11] which is extension of Mindlin plate theory to anisotropic plates, the displacements are assumed to be of the form

$$\begin{aligned} u_x^*(x,y,z) &= u^{0*}(x,y) + z\phi_x^*(x,y) \\ u_y^*(x,y,z) &= v^{0*}(x,y) + z\phi_y^*(x,y) \\ u_z^*(x,y) &= w^*(x,y) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The resultant forces and moments are obtained by integrating the stress, given in Eq.(5), through the laminate thickness. They become as follows for the transverse vibration of symmetric laminate:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} M_x^* \\ M_y^* \\ M_{xy}^* \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} D_{11}^* & D_{12}^* & D_{16}^* \\ D_{12}^* & D_{22}^* & D_{26}^* \\ D_{16}^* & D_{26}^* & D_{66}^* \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \phi_{x,x}^* \\ \phi_{y,y}^* \\ \phi_{x,y}^* + \phi_{y,x}^* \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \begin{Bmatrix} Q_y^* \\ Q_x^* \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{44}^* & A_{45}^* \\ A_{45}^* & A_{55}^* \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} w_{,y}^* + \phi_y^* \\ w_{,x}^* + \phi_x^* \end{Bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

where $D_{ij}^* = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} (\bar{Q}_{ij}^*)_k z^2 dz$ and $A_{ij}^* = \bar{k} \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} (\bar{Q}_{ij}^*)_k dz$. The value of \bar{k} is the shear correction factor.

The governing equation can be obtained by substituting Eq.(7) into the equilibrium equation of plate and assuming sinusoidal motion.

$$\begin{aligned} & [A_{45}^* (w_{,y}^* + \phi_y^*) + A_{55}^* (w_{,x}^* + \phi_x^*)]_{,x} \\ & + [A_{44}^* (w_{,y}^* + \phi_y^*) + A_{45}^* (w_{,x}^* + \phi_x^*)]_{,y} = -\lambda^* P w^* \end{aligned} \quad (8.a)$$

$$[D_{11}^* \phi_{x,x}^* + D_{12}^* \phi_{y,y}^* + D_{16}^* (\phi_{x,y}^* + \phi_{y,x}^*)]_{,x} + [D_{16}^* \phi_{x,x}^* + D_{26}^* \phi_{y,y}^* + D_{66}^* (\phi_{x,y}^* + \phi_{y,x}^*)]_{,y} - A_{45}^* (w_{,y}^* + \phi_y^*) - A_{55}^* (w_{,x}^* + \phi_x^*) = -\lambda^* I \phi_x^* \quad (8.b)$$

$$[D_{16}^* \phi_{x,x}^* + D_{26}^* \phi_{y,y}^* + D_{66}^* (\phi_{x,y}^* + \phi_{y,x}^*)]_{,x} + [D_{12}^* \phi_{x,x}^* + D_{22}^* \phi_{y,y}^* + D_{26}^* (\phi_{x,y}^* + \phi_{y,x}^*)]_{,y} - A_{44}^* (w_{,y}^* + \phi_y^*) - A_{45}^* (w_{,x}^* + \phi_x^*) = -\lambda^* I \phi_y^* \quad (8.c)$$

where $(P, I) = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} (1, z^2) \rho dz$ and comma denotes partial differentiation.

Finite element formulation of Eq.(8) gives the complex generalized eigenvalue problem.

$$\begin{bmatrix} [K_{11}^*] & [K_{12}^*] & [K_{13}^*] \\ & [K_{22}^*] & [K_{23}^*] \\ \text{sym.} & & [K_{33}^*] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{w^*\} \\ \{\phi_x^*\} \\ \{\phi_y^*\} \end{Bmatrix} - \lambda^* \begin{bmatrix} [M_{11}] & [0] & [0] \\ & [M_{22}] & [0] \\ \text{sym.} & & [M_{33}] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{w^*\} \\ \{\phi_x^*\} \\ \{\phi_y^*\} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

where eigenvalue, λ^* and eigenvector are complex number.

2.3 Modal approach Since Eq.(9) is the complex eigenvalue problem with large d.o.f., it requires tremendous amount of computation time. Therefore a modal approach should be adopted, which is common in flutter analysis of aircraft wing. Rewriting Eq.(9) in the following matrix form,

$$[K^* - \lambda^* M] u^* = 0. \quad (10)$$

Eigenvector, u^* can be transformed into q^* using the associated modal matrix, Φ which is obtained from the free vibration analysis for the composite plate without considering damping effect.

$$u^* = \Phi q^* \quad (11)$$

,where $\Phi = [\phi_1 \phi_2 \phi_3 \cdots \phi_N]$ in the case of taking N modes.

Premultiplying Eq.(10) with Φ^T and substituting Eq.(11) into Eq.(10),

$$\Phi^T [K^* - \lambda^* M] \Phi q^* = 0. \quad (12)$$

As a result, the dimension of Eq.(12) is reduced to N.

The reduced eigenvalue problem, Eq.(12) gives the natural frequency ω_n and modal loss factor η_n for each mode as follows:

$$\omega_n^2 = \text{Re}[\lambda_n^*], \quad \eta_n = \frac{\text{Im}[\lambda_n^*]}{\text{Re}[\lambda_n^*]}. \quad (13)$$

The magnitude of complex eigenvector is mode shape and the ratio of an imaginary part to a real part represents a phase angle. The free vibration analysis is performed by using IMSL subroutine, EIGZS to obtain modal matrix, and then the complex eigenvalue problem is solved by using IMSL subroutine, EIGZC [12].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 All-free laminates The composite laminates used in this paper consists of HMS carbon fiber in DX-210 epoxy resin (see Table 1). η_{23} is taken as the same value as η_{12} since it does not affect the computational results. Plate data used in this analysis are detailed in Table 2. The convergence test results of natural frequencies for plate 762 in Table 2 are given in Fig. 3. The natural frequencies for 5×5 elements are regarded as converged. The loss factors was not affected by the number of modes in the modal approach, which was ten excluding rigid body modes. Table 3 shows the comparison between present results and Lin's results [3] for the natural frequencies and the modal loss factors. The present result gives a good agreement with Lin's result which was obtained by using the material properties corrected from a standard set given for a 0.5 fiber volume fraction.

In order to study the variation of natural frequency and modal loss factor with fiber orientation, the material properties in Table 1 and the plate data for plate 762 in Table 2 are used except for the stacking sequence of $[0/\pm\theta/90]_s$. Fig. 4 shows the modal loss factor for the first mode of which the typical shape is pure torsion due to in-plane shear at $\theta = 0^\circ$ and $\theta = 90^\circ$. The plate for the fiber orientation besides $\theta = 0^\circ$ and $\theta = 90^\circ$ have less damping by virtue of bending-torsion coupling. Fig.5 shows the natural frequency and modal loss factor for the 2nd mode. The reason for higher value of modal loss factors in the range of $\theta = 0^\circ - 20^\circ$ is that energy dissipation is occurred in the form of matrix tension/compression. As the fiber orientation increases, tension/compression in fibers retains the strain energy to increase the natural frequency and decrease the modal loss factor. Fig. 6 shows the third mode whose shape is twisting. When the fiber orientation, θ is zero degree, the twisting deformation results in the large amount of tension/compression in the matrix of $\pm\theta$ layer. Therefore, the natural frequency is the lowest and the modal loss factor is the highest at $\theta = 0^\circ$. However, when the fiber orientation, θ increases, the stresses of tension/compression increase in the fiber of $\pm\theta$ layer. Hence, the total trends of the composite plate change due to the fiber orientation. Fig. 7 depicts the result for the 4th mode. The severe change in mode shape occurs near $\theta = 35^\circ$.

The results in Fig.4 - 7 are obtained under the assumption that the material properties in fiber direction are perfectly elastic and others are viscoelastic. This approximate method uses zero as the value of η_{11} and η_1 of DX-210/BF400 as the value of η_{22} , η_{12} , η_{13} , and η_{23} . From these results it might be concluded that the approximate method gives reasonable solution only for matrix shearing mode. The mode shapes of the real and imaginary parts for $\theta = 30^\circ$ are given in Fig. 8 where s.f. is a scale factor. Because the values of imaginary parts are very small compared with those of real parts, the real parts can be considered as total mode shapes. Fig. 9 shows the contour plots of lateral displacement for both $\theta = 0^\circ$ and $\theta = 45^\circ$.

3.2 Simply-supported laminates For simply supported laminates, the material properties in reference [6] is used (see Table 4). Alam assumed that loss factor associated with E_1 is negligible and those associated with other moduli are 0.5, which seem to be rare for the common commercial composite materials. For the sake of comparison, however, those values are used in this paper. The number of element used for the computation is 4×6 for $AR = 0.25$, 6×6 for $AR = 1.00$, and 6×4 for $AR = 4.00$. From Table 5, it is found that frequency parameter, λ_T is of good agreement at $\theta = 0^\circ$ and $\theta = 90^\circ$. The discrepancy increases as θ increases to 45° because Alam ignored bending-torsion coupling by assuming angle-ply laminate to be specially orthotropic. In fact, since $D_{11} = 0.4583$ and $D_{16} = D_{26} = 0.2395$ for $\theta = 45^\circ$, D_{16} and D_{26} could not be assumed as zero compared with D_{11} . Table 5 shows the computational results for two cases; full mode by Eq. (9) and modal approach with 10 modes. Modal approach gives very accurate results and can save tremendous amount of computation time. Although there seem to be relatively large errors near $\theta = 0^\circ$ for $AR = 0.25$ and $\theta = 90^\circ$ for $AR = 4.00$, this stems from the assumption of large loss factors, i.e. 0.5. Thus those errors can be neglected, compared with other values.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The shear deformable plate theory is applied to the vibration and damping analysis of the fiber-reinforced composite laminates. The complex eigenvalue problem using finite element method is solved by the modal approach, which gives reasonable results and reduces computation time. The effect of the fiber orientation on the natural frequencies and the modal loss factors is investigated. The modal loss factor is greatly affected by mode shape, and is large when matrix is subjected to shearing and tension/compression deformations. The numerical result obtained under the assumption that the material properties in the fiber direction are perfectly elastic and the others are viscoelastic, is valid only for twisting mode.

5. REFERENCES

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Table 1. Material properties used by Lin *et. al.* [3].

Material	E_1 GPa	E_2 GPa	G_{12} GPa	η_1	η_2	η_{12}	ν_{12}	V_f
HMS/DX-210	172.7	7.2	3.76	7.162×10^{-4}	6.716×10^{-3}	1.122×10^{-2}	0.3	0.5
DX-210/BF400	3.21	3.21	1.20	1.041×10^{-2}	1.041×10^{-2}	1.064×10^{-2}	0.34	0.0

Table 2. Plate data used by Lin *et. al.* [3].

Plate Number	No. of Layers	Density kg/m ³	Thickness mm	a(=b) mm	V_f	Stacking Sequence
762	8	1566	1.58	178	0.516	[0/0/0/0]s
770	8	1551.4	1.62	215	0.494	[0/90/45/-45]s

Table 3. Natural frequencies and modal loss factors for all-free laminates.

Plate Number	Mode	Natural Frequency (Hz)			Modal Loss Factor ($\times 10^{-2}$)		
		Modal Approach	Lin <i>et. al.</i> [3]		Modal Approach	Lin <i>et. al.</i> [3]	
			FEM	Exp.		FEM	Exp.
762	1	81.63	83.57	81.5	1.0983	1.0759	1.1141
	2	110.08	118.42	107.4	0.6675	0.6821	0.7799
	3	199.43	207.79	196.6	0.9656	0.9374	0.8594
	4	306.13	329.41	295.5	0.6686	0.6573	0.7480
	5	396.84	419.83	382.5	0.8407	0.8133	0.7639
	6	538.26	546.93	531.0	0.0781	0.0748	-
770	1	87.52	86.33	77.8	0.4827	0.4950	0.6525
	2	226.67	224.49	202.7	0.1228	0.1273	0.1464
	3	282.70	280.42	258.0	0.2647	0.2706	0.2706
	4	301.93	298.81	298.7	0.0936	0.0923	0.1225
	5	351.93	348.36	322.0	0.1870	0.1894	0.1910
	6	515.32	512.24	496.7	0.2880	0.2881	0.3342

Table 4. Material properties used by Alam and Asnani [6].

Material	E_1	E_2	G_{12}	G_{13}	G_{23}	ν_{12}	ρ
CFRP	211 GPa	5.3 GPa	2.6 GPa	2.6 GPa	1.3 GPa	0.25	1882 kg/m ³

Loss factor associated with E_1 is negligible, and all the others are 0.5.

Table 5. λ_c and η of the first mode for simply supported $[\pm\theta]$ s laminates.

a/b	θ	$\lambda_c (\times 10^8)$		Loss factor, η		
		Present	Alam[6]	Present		
				Full mode	Modal Approach.	Alam[6]
0.25	0	0.10065	0.100	0.00350	0.00381	0.0029
	15	0.08934	0.0898	0.00606	0.00636	0.0044
	30	0.06211	0.0646	0.01607	0.01633	0.0103
	45	0.03356	0.0366	0.04385	0.04425	0.0272
	60	0.01463	0.0162	0.11382	0.11453	0.077
	75	0.00584	0.00598	0.25937	0.26011	0.229
	90	0.00332	0.00327	0.44096	0.44103	0.429
1.00	0	0.10882	0.108	0.04143	0.04178	0.036
	15	0.11944	0.132	0.04352	0.04401	0.027
	30	0.14606	0.180	0.03964	0.04020	0.0168
	45	0.15705	0.204	0.03595	0.03643	0.0135
	0	0.84296	0.838	0.44103	0.44111	0.429
4.00	15	1.4507	1.53	0.26907	0.27039	0.231
	30	3.5952	4.1	0.12054	0.12228	0.0815
	45	8.2830	9.23	0.05344	0.05620	0.0343
	60	15.286	16.1	0.03191	0.03599	0.022
	75	21.921	22.2	0.02557	0.03053	0.0212
	90	24.681	24.6	0.02381	0.02897	0.022

Fig. 1. Complex modulus and loss angle.

Fig.2. Coordinate systems of geometric axes and principal material axes.

Fig. 3. Convergence of natural frequencies of plate 762 (Natural frequencies are normalized by those for 6x6 elements).

Fig. 4. Natural frequencies and modal loss factors (L.F.) of the 1st mode for all-free $[0/\pm\theta /90]_s$ laminate.

Fig. 5. Natural frequencies and modal loss factors (L.F.) of the 2nd mode for all-free $[0/\pm\theta /90]_s$ laminate.

Fig. 6. Natural frequencies and modal loss factors (L.F.) of the 3rd mode for all-free $[0/\pm\theta /90]_s$ laminate.

Fig. 7. Natural frequencies and modal loss factors (L.F.) of the 4th mode for all-free $[0/\pm\theta /90]_s$ laminate.

Fig. 8. Real and imaginary parts of mode shapes for all-free $[0/\pm\theta /90]_s$ laminate ($\theta = 30^\circ$). s.f. : scale factor.

Fig. 9. Contour plots for all-free $[0/\pm\theta/90]_s$ laminate (* denotes nodal line).

BIOGRAPHY

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